

Ash, Protein, Ether Extract and Carbohydrate Contents of Sorghum Genotypes Silages Grown at Eskişehir Condition

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Abstract

Global warming, water scarcity, and the increasing demand for food have led growers and researchers to alternative products and methods. Therefore, sorghum, which can be grown in hot and dry conditions, has come to the forefront in recent years. For this purpose, 10 sorghum lines (104, 112, 301, 302, 304, 32-1, 8, G310, K311) and 12 registered sorghum varieties (Aldarı, Beydarı, E:Sumuc, Erdurmuş, Greengo, Gözde 80, Haybuster, Leoti, Nes, Öğretmenoğlu, Uzun, Rox) were examined in Eskişehir and similar ecologies to determine their silage contents. In the study, the contents of ash, soluble protein, ether extract, sugar, and carbohydrate were examined. Significant differences were found in all the examined traits among the lines and varieties. The average crude ash of the sorghum genotypes was determined to be 3.81%, soluble protein 52.54%, crude fat 1.48%, sugar 7.59%, and fiber content 63.92%. For silage production in Eskişehir province and similar ecological conditions, sorghum genotypes with high sugar content, particularly lines B305 and 8, as well as the Greengo and Leoti varieties, are recommended for cultivation.

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1. Introduction

The inadequacy of feed resources has made meeting the nutritional needs of animals an important issue. One of the biggest challenges faced by livestock farming in Turkey is the shortage of roughage that occurs during the winter months. To close the roughage gap and meet the increasing demand, production policies and storage methods need to change. Therefore, silage plays an important role in feeding animals, especially during the winter months, by meeting the increasing demand and providing a sustainable food source (Tenikecier and Ateş, 2024). One of the most preferred plants for silage production is sorghum.

Due to its superior characteristics, such as being more resistant to dry and hot conditions compared to corn (Li et al., 2010) and its ability to grow in saline soils (Kimber, 2000), the importance of the sorghum plant is increasing in these areas (Almodares and Hadi, 2009). The resistance of sorghum species and hybrids to diseases and pests (Awika and Rooney, 2004) contributes to reducing chemical use in the control diseases, pests, and weeds, and supports sustainable agricultural practices. It performs better than corn in terms of root formation (House, 1985), water use efficiency and nutrient use (Bean et al., 2002). At the same time, its ability to thrive in a wide variety of soil types, pH levels (Kimber, 2000), and high temperatures further enhances its importance in arid and semi-arid regions (Bahrani and Deghani Ghenatghehstani, 2004). The low production cost is also a significant advantage of sorghum. The fact that it requires less seed, 30% less fertilizer, and water compared to corn silage makes sorghum an economical alternative. (Pino and Heinrichs, 2017). Sorghum silage, which has high nutritional value and digestibility, contributes to the sustainability of livestock farming by meeting the nutritional needs of animals (Türedi and Çetingül, 2023; Erkovan and Afacan, 2024).

Sorghum, due to its low production cost and its potential as an alternative plant for species that require a lot of water in the face of global

climate change-induced water scarcity, is becoming increasingly important (Çiğdem and Uzun, 2006). At the same time, varieties of sorghum species and hybrids, cultivated for silage, green fodder, grazing, and grain production, contribute to closing the gap in roughage and have significant potential to enhance sustainability in livestock farming (Awika and Rooney, 2004). This study was conducted to investigate the silage potential and some silage characteristics of different sorghum lines and varieties with various uses that can be cultivated in Eskişehir and similar ecologies.

2. Material and Methods

This study conducted in the experimental fields of the Faculty of Agriculture at Eskişehir Osmangazi University following the 2023 wheat harvest, 22 sorghum genotypes (8, 12, 32-1, 104, 301, 302, 304, B305, G310, K311, Aldarı, Beydarı, Öğretmenoğlu, Uzun, Erdurmuş, Gözde-80, Greengo, Haybuster, E:Sumoc, Rox, Leoti, Nes) were used. The soils of the experimental area are clay-loamy (Soil Survey Division Staff, 1992), medium calcareous (14.61%) (Ülgen and Yurtsever, 1995), slightly alkaline (7.68%) (Ülgen and Yurtsever, 1995), unsaline (0.07%), low in terms of organic matter (1.62%) (Ülgen ve Yurtsever, 1995), very high in potassium (168.80 kg da⁻¹), and adequate in phosphorus content (6.16 kg da⁻¹) (Ülgen and Yurtsever, 1995). The average total rainfall in Eskişehir province, where a continental climate prevails, is 291.7 mm according to the long-term average. The highest monthly rainfall during the vegetation period was in June (62.0 mm). According to the long-term average, the highest temperature was 21.5 °C in July and 21.4 °C in August, while the lowest temperature was -0.2 °C in January. In the year 2023, when the experiment was conducted, the relative humidity (66.4%) was higher than the long-term average relative humidity (61.7%) (Table 1). The experimental design were established in a randomized block design with three replications. Each plot is 5 m long and consists of 5 rows. The planting area was

processed after the wheat harvest, and the plots were prepared for sowing. The sowing operation was carried out on June 15, 2023, with sorghum seeds manually sown in rows 0.6 m at a rate of 2.5 kg da⁻¹ (Açıköz, 1995). In the experimental area, diammonium phosphate was applied to the plots as a base fertilizer at a rate of 2 kg da⁻¹ of nitrogen and 5 kg da⁻¹ of phosphorus. In the study, weed control was performed manually when the sorghum plants were approximately 20-25 cm tall. Following the weed control, nitrogen fertilizer (Ammonium sulfate) was applied at a rate of 15 kg da⁻¹. Irrigation was carried out by sprinkling until reaching the field capacity of the soil during the period they needed it. Harvesting was done by hand at the dough maturity period of the plants.

The harvested plants were chopped into 0.5-1 cm pieces using a mechanical shredding machine and then ensiled. To balance the

effect of particle size, all samples were subjected to the same mechanical processing without the addition of any additives. After the samples were fragmented, they were filled into silage bags, which were then vacuumed and tightly sealed to prevent air from entering the bags. The experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with 6 replications. The silage bags were opened after an 8-week fermentation period. A 500 g sample from each bag was dried at 70 °C to constant weight, and dry matter content was determined. The samples were then ground to pass through a 2 mm sieve for further analysis of ether extract, soluble crude protein, crude ash, sugar contents and carbohydrate using FT-NIR (Fourier Transform Near-Infrared Spectroscopy). The data were analyzed using the SAS statistical software, and significant means were compared using Scheffe's multiple comparison tests (SAS Institute, 1998).

Table 1. Some climate data of the area where the experiment was conducted between 1928 and 2023

Months	2023 Year			Long-term average		
	Tempurate °C	Precipitation mm	Relative Humidity %	Tempurate °C	Precipitation mm	Relative Humidity %
January	3.5	16.5	77.8	-0.2	40.0	75.2
February	2.5	15.0	70.3	1.4	32.8	71.0
March	7.4	115.7	76.1	5.0	35.3	65.0
April	10.7	41.1	64.8	10.2	38.4	62.4
May	14.5	59.6	71.9	15.0	44.9	59.9
June	19.4	62.0	67.3	18.9	33.6	55.0
July	23.6	0.6	50.6	21.5	13.2	51.8
August	25.9	0.1	49.9	21.4	8.7	52.9
September	19.9	21.2	59.2	17.4	15.9	58.4
October	15.3	24.8	76.4	12.9	28.9	65.2
Total	---	356.6	---	---	291.7	---
Average	14.3	---	66.4	12.4	---	61.7

3. Results

In this study conducted to determine the silage content of some sorghum genotypes grown after wheat harvest, the crude ash, soluble protein, ether extract, sugar, and carbohydrate contents of sorghum lines and varieties were determined. According to the research results, statistically significant differences were found among the sorghum genotypes in terms of ash, ether extract, sugar, and carbohydrate contents. In terms of soluble

protein content, no statistically significant differences were found. The ash content of different sorghum genotypes was found to be lowest at 1.57% in line 12 and highest at 6.93% in the G310 line and Uzun variety (Table 2) (Figure 1). The average crude ash content was determined to be 3.81% (Table 2). Among the sorghum genotypes silage, it was observed that the ash content of lines numbered 301, 32-1, 8, G310, K311, as well as the Aldarı, Erdurmuş, Gözde-80 Nes, and Uzun varieties, was above average (Table 2).

Figure 1. The crude ash content (%) of sorghum lines and varieties

The soluble protein ratio of the sorghum genotypes grown and ensiled under the ecological conditions of Eskişehir was determined to be an average of 52.54% (Table

2). In the study, all sorghum genotypes, except for the E:Sumoc (49.93%) and Haybuster (49.37%) varieties, had a soluble protein ratio above 50% (Table 2, Figure 2).

Table 2. Average crude ash, soluble protein, oil, sugar and row fiber ratios and statistical values of sorghum genotypes

Varieties/lines	Crude ash (%)	Soluable protein (%)	Ether extract (%)	Sugar content (%)	Carbohydrates (%)
104	2.77	52.80	0.93	6.53	62.87
12	1.57	52.23	0.90	6.73	64.97
301	5.07	54.77	2.33	8.70	83.30
302	1.83	53.37	1.03	7.87	61.37
304	3.50	52.33	1.27	7.03	70.20
32-1	4.17	50.40	1.20	7.13	82.03
8	4.57	51.90	1.23	8.83	62.60
Aldarı	4.27	56.50	0.60	6.90	74.20
B305	2.30	51.17	1.77	9.47	51.80
Beydarı	3.50	50.00	1.70	7.80	62.23
E: Sumoc	2.90	49.93	0.97	8.00	53.97
Erdurmuş	5.90	54.37	2.23	7.83	60.13
G310	6.93	52.83	2.00	6.87	68.90
Gözde 80	5.03	54.63	1.50	8.57	66.87
Greengo	3.90	52.43	1.83	9.03	60.43
Haybuster	2.20	49.37	1.30	6.13	49.00
K311	4.20	52.63	1.50	7.50	59.03
Leoti	2.70	56.23	1.83	8.63	65.37
Nes	3.83	50.40	1.33	6.57	55.17
Öğretmenoğlu	3.63	54.73	1.37	6.80	66.70
Rox	2.07	50.63	1.53	6.97	70.43
Uzun	6.93	52.17	2.20	7.07	54.70
Average	3.81	52.54	1.48	7.59	63.92
F Value	23.424	1.434	4.743	3.950	18.714
P Value	.0001	.1550	.0001	.0001	.0001

Figure 2. Soluble protein content (%) of sorghum genotypes

The ether extract content of the silages of the sorghum genotypes ranged from 0.60% to 2.33% and was recorded as an average of 1.48% (Table 2). Among the sorghum genotypes, the highest ether extract content

was found to be 2.33% in line 301, while the other genotypes had lower ether extract content compared to line 301 (Table 2, Figure 3).

Figure 3. The crude oil content (%) of sorghum genotypes silage under Eskişehir conditions

The sugar content of the silage sorghum genotypes was lowest in the Haybuster variety (6.13%) and highest in the B305 line (9.47%),

while the average sugar content of the sorghum lines and varieties was determined to be 7.59% (Table 2, Figure 4).

Figure 4. The sugar contents (%) of the sorghum genotypes under consideration

The average carbohydrate content has been determined to be 63.92% (Table 2). While line 301 had the highest content (83.30%), it was found that the carbohydrate contents of lines

12, 301, 304 32-1, G310, as well as the varieties Aldarı, Gözde-80, Leoti, Öğretmenoğlu, and Rox were above average (Table 2, Figure 5).

Figure 5. Carbohydrate contents (%) of sorghum silages

4. Discussion

The ash content in a plant consists of the non-combustible residue left after the dry

matter is burned, and it provides information about the plant's mineral content (Gençtan, 1998). Therefore, in roughage feeds, high ash

content is desired (Geren et al., 2014). The reason for this is that the feed is rich in micro and macro elements, and these elements are essential sources in animal nutrition. These minerals, which are not synthesized by animal organisms, must be obtained externally (Aydoğan and Demiroğlu Topçu, 2022). In silage crops, the crude ash content varies depending on factors such as genetic structures, plant species, environmental factors, and planting time (Kılınç, 2022). Significant differences in ash content have been recorded among the genotypes examined. The main reason for the difference in crude ash content among the sorghum genotypes grown in the same environment and harvested at the same developmental stage is due to the genetic differences among the materials considered. The sorghum genotypes used can be utilized for different purposes. Therefore, it is expected that the ash content will differ. Soluble protein is defined as proteins within protein particles with a diameter of <40 nm (Ono et al., 1991), and it is assumed that these are different monomers of the subunits of soy protein. Depending on the conditions, they can either be free in aqueous environments or surrounded by fats, and they are found in all parts of the plant (Goni, 2001). The soluble protein ratios of the examined genotypes do not show any differences. The lack of variation in soluble proteins may be due to the same environment and cultivation conditions, even though the genetic and usage purposes differ. Ether extract are one of the energy sources included in the rations of ruminants, and their total energy content is higher than that of carbohydrates. Therefore, ether extract are needed in rations to increase the energy content of the feed (Arslan and Çakmakçı, 2011, Andrea et al., 2000). The ether extract content that should be present in cattle rations generally varies between 2-5% (Küçük and Özpınar, 2004). In feeds with very high ether extract content, dry matter consumption decreases and the digestion of some minerals becomes difficult, while low ether extract content can lead to reduced energy and productivity (Arslan and Çakmakçı, 2011). The ether extract of sorghum grains varies

according to genotypes, ecological characteristics, and cultural practices (Ebadi et al., 2005, Baydar 2000). Significant differences in ether extract content were recorded among the genotypes examined in this study. The main reason for the difference in ether extract content among the sorghum genotypes grown in the same environment and harvested at the same developmental stage is due to the genetic differences among the materials considered. The sugar content in sorghum silage plays an important role in the effective fermentation process and the production of high-quality silage (Basmacıoğlu and Ergül, 2002). Plants with high soluble carbohydrate content, such as sorghum, create an ideal environment for lactic acid bacteria by lowering the pH of the environment during fermentation. This increases the quantity of silage and ensures its preservation, while low sugar content leads to the formation of undesirable microorganisms. Therefore, the high sugar content in sorghum silage provides a significant advantage for the healthy development of fermentation and the prevention of undesirable micro flora growth (Davies et al., 1998). Significant differences in sugar content were recorded among the genotypes examined in this study. The main reason for the difference in sugar content among the sorghum genotypes, which are grown in the same environment and harvested at the same developmental stage for silage, is due to the genetic differences among the materials being studied. Sorghums contain a high amount of structural carbohydrates that can be used as fiber. In the study in question, it has been determined that there is a high content of structural carbohydrates, similar to the previous findings. It is expected that the silage obtained from sorghum genotypes with different genetic and usage characteristics will also have different carbohydrate content. The differences in plant height, stem, and leaf ratio among sorghum genotypes grown under similar conditions also lead to variations in the structural carbohydrate content of the silages (Widowati and Luna, 2022). Indeed, it has been stated in the studies conducted that the differences in plant characteristics also lead to

differences in the structural carbohydrate content (Widowati and Luna, 2022). In conclusion, when examining the quality characteristics of the silages of sorghum genotypes planted after the wheat harvest, the highest crude ash content was obtained from line G310 and the Uzun variety, while the highest soluble protein content was obtained from the Aldarı variety. The ether extract and carbohydrate contents of the sorghum lines and varieties were found to be highest in line 301. Among the sorghum genotypes used for silage, it has been determined that the B305 line has the highest sugar content. The findings suggest that cultivating sorghum genotypes as silage can provide high-quality roughage needed for animal production. In Eskişehir and similar ecological conditions, sorghum genotypes specified as alternatives for a short-term vegetative period as a second crop can be recommended.

Author Contributions Statement

All authors declare that they contributed equally to this manuscript, have seen/read the final version of the manuscript, and approve it for publication.

Conflict of Interest Statement

All authors declare no conflict of interest in relation to this study.

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